

The Doping Mechanism of Halide Perovskite Unveiled by Alkaline Earth Metals

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Abstract

Halide perovskites are a strong candidate for the next generation of photovoltaics. Chemical doping of halide perovskites is an established strategy to prepare the highest efficiency and most stable perovskite-based solar cells. In this study, we unveil the doping mechanism of halide perovskites using a series of alkaline earth metals. We find that low doping levels enable the incorporation of the dopant within the perovskite lattice, whereas high doping concentrations induce surface segregation. The threshold from low to high doping regime correlates to the size of the doping element. We show that the low doping regime results in a more n-type material, while the high doping regime induces a less n-type doping character. Our work provides a comprehensive picture of the unique doping mechanism of halide perovskites, which differs from classical semiconductors. We proved the effectiveness of the low doping regime for the first time, demonstrating highly efficient methylammonium lead iodide based solar cells in both n-i-p and p-i-n architectures.

Introduction

Halide perovskite absorbers have enabled solar cells with more than 25% power conversion efficiency (PCE) on a lab-scale, which makes them potentially competitive with established thin-film technologies such as those based on CdTe and Cu(In, Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) absorbers.⁽¹⁾ This class of material has a general composition of ABX₃, where A is a monovalent cation (e.g. methylammonium (MA)), B is a divalent cation (e.g. Pb), and X is a halide. The so-called 3D halide perovskites consist of cation A residing in a cage made of corner sharing octahedra BX₆. The addition of a small number of foreign ions into the perovskite precursor solution is a well-known strategy to improve the efficiency of perovskite-based solar cells (PSCs).^(2–5) In the majority of the cases, the addition of foreign ions results in the segregation at the surface of the perovskite crystals as a secondary phase, which may still have a positive impact on the device performance⁽⁶⁾ while leaving the perovskite crystal structure unchanged.⁽⁷⁾

Ionic radii control whether or not foreign cations can be incorporated into the perovskite lattice. For instance, the monovalent ions Rb, K, and Na are too small to be included stably into the lattice. However, they improve PSCs performance by influencing the crystallization and the surface defect chemistry.^(6,8) Divalent ions such as alkaline earth metals Sr, Ca, and Mg, or transition metals such as Cd and Co have also been explored.^(2,9–13) In particular, theoretical calculations have predicted Sr²⁺ to replace Pb²⁺ in the perovskite lattice, as Sr²⁺ and Pb²⁺ have similar ionic radii, while Mg²⁺ cannot.^(9,11,14,15) Sr²⁺ has enabled significant efficiency enhancement in PSCs; however, it remains unclear how much Sr²⁺ can actually be incorporated in the perovskite lattice. Considering that the ionic radii of Sr²⁺ and Mg²⁺ in bonding with six halides are 118 and 72 pm, respectively,⁽¹⁶⁾ these ionic radii, thus, can be translated directly to the bond length of B-X in the octahedron of the 3D perovskite structure. In particular, Sr-I bond length is the summation of Sr²⁺ radius and I⁻ radius. The tolerance factor is defined as $t = (r_A + r_X) / (\sqrt{2}(r_B + r_X))$,⁽¹⁷⁾ where the MA⁺ radius is taken as 217 pm and I⁻ is 220 pm. Hence, the tolerance factor for Sr²⁺ and Mg²⁺ replacing Pb²⁺ (119 pm) in 3D MA-based perovskite structure is 0.91 and 1.06, respectively. To form a 3D perovskite structure, the tolerance factor of the compound should be in the range of 0.8 to 1.0.^(18,19) Therefore, Sr²⁺ is expected to form a MASrI₃ 3D halide perovskite, whereas Mg²⁺ is not a suitable candidate. However, a purely synthesized 3D MASrI₃ halide perovskite has not yet been reported by the time of this study.^(10,11) In fact, several studies have observed that Sr-doped perovskite films exhibit Sr-rich phases at the surface, which may modify the interfacial energy alignment between perovskite and the charge selective contact layers in PSCs.^(20–22)

Here, we use Sr²⁺ and Mg²⁺ as representative cations to investigate the size dependence doping mechanism of halide perovskites. Combining theoretical and experimental investigations, including synchrotron-based characterizations of the materials and device integration, we identify two doping regimes. At relatively high doping levels (3–10 mol%), such as those most commonly used in literature, the dopant is likely to segregate in a secondary phase at the surface of the perovskite. Conversely, at concentrations significantly lower (0.1–1 mol%) the dopants are incorporated into the perovskite lattice. The threshold between the low- and high-doping regime depends on the size of the dopant. We show that the low doping regime induces a more n-type material while the high doping regime induces a less n-type doping character of the perovskite semiconductor. Such behavior is peculiar of halide perovskites and somewhat different from doping of classical semiconductors. We prove the low-doping regime as a new strategy to enhance the efficiency of perovskite solar cells, demonstrating MAPbI₃-based devices with an open circuit voltage exceeding 1.16 V and a stabilized power conversion efficiency exceeding 19% in a p-i-n and 20% in an n-i-p solar cell.

Results and Discussion

Doping Mechanism

The formation of halide perovskites is associated with the existence of lattice defects as for any crystalline material. Density functional theory (DFT) calculations have shown that Schottky defects, which form when oppositely charged ions leave their lattice sites creating vacancies, contribute to the defects density in halide perovskites most significantly.(23–25) The calculated concentration of the Schottky defects in the perovskite lattice spans from 10^{10} up to 10^{20} cm^{-3} .(23–25) Given that the Pb^{2+} concentration in a perfect perovskite crystal is in the range of 10^{21} cm^{-3} , we rationalize that the defect concentrations in halide perovskite should not be higher than 1% of the Pb^{2+} . Therefore, if chemical doping is explored for the healing of harmful defects, the doping should be in subpercent molar. However, most of the works in the literature report significantly higher doping levels to demonstrate improved PSCs performances.(13,20,21,26–28)

We hypothesize that a limited amount of dopant, which depends on the atomic size of the doping element, can be incorporated into the perovskite lattice and thus interact with the defect chemistry of the material. To demonstrate our hypothesis, we focus on Sr^{2+} and Mg^{2+} since they have similar chemical properties (elements in the same chemical group) but have different ionic radii (118 and 72 pm, respectively).(16) DFT shows that the incorporation of Sr^{2+} and Mg^{2+} in MAPbI_3 may occur through various processes: (i) Pb^{2+} substitution (Sr_{Pb} or Mg_{Pb}); (ii) interstitial (Sr_i^{2+} or Mg_i^{2+}); (iii) MA^+ substitution (Sr_{MA^+} or Mg_{MA^+}) as all illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Figure 1. Potential doping mechanism calculated by DFT. Visualization of Sr doping (depicted in yellow) (a) Pb^{2+} substitution by Sr^{2+} (Sr_{Pb}), (b) interstitial Sr^{2+} (Sr_i^{2+}), and (c) methylammonium (MA) substitution by Sr^{2+} (Sr_{MA^+}). Similarly, Mg doping (depicted in green) as (d) Pb^{2+} substitution by Mg^{2+} (Mg_{Pb}), (e) interstitial Mg^{2+} (Mg_i^{2+}), and (f) MA substitution by Mg^{2+} (Mg_{MA^+}).

Doping in the Silicon system involves the dopants providing extra electrons or holes to the Si network.(29) Changes in intrinsic point defect concentrations that shift the Fermi level (E_F) occur in CIGS absorbers,(30) and to some extent are also found in halide perovskites.(31) However, this kind of doping is tuned by the growth method(32) without any extrinsic dopants like in doping of Si. Herein, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first report on doping a halide perovskite by intentional manipulation of the defect chemistry of the material by extrinsic dopants. The dopants (Sr and Mg) incorporation or segregation can change the defect concentrations in MAPbI_3 . Depending on the doping regime, the (net) n-type doping of the perovskite is either increased or decreased. It is rather surprising that *one* dopant can introduce more or less n-type doping depending on the concentration, which is different from classical doping. The threshold between the low- and high-doping regimes depends on the size of the dopant, which will be discussed in more detail in the next sections.

Effect of Different Doping Regimes on Material Property

We employed hard X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (HAXPES) to examine the chemical composition of doped perovskite layers. The same substrate and deposition procedure used for the preparation of PSCs were used to rule out any possible side effects (see [Methods section](#)). (33) [Figure 2a,b](#) presents the quantified [Sr]:[Pb] and [Mg]:[Pb] ratios derived from the HAXPES core levels (i.e., Sr 3p_{3/2}, Mg 1s, and Pb 4f_{7/2}) measured with excitation energies of 2 and 6 keV (the corresponding 2 and 6 keV excited HAXPES spectra are shown in [Figure S2 and Figure S3](#), see [SI](#)). By using different excitation energies, it is possible to vary the probing depths of the HAXPES measurements. For the Sr 3p and Pb 4f lines, the analyses using 2 and 6 keV result in photoelectron inelastic mean free paths (IMFP) of ≈ 4 nm and ≈ 10 nm, respectively (see [Methods section](#) for more details on how IMFP relates to probing depth). (34,35) [Figure 2a](#) shows that the [Sr]:[Pb] ratios computed from the 6 keV (i.e., more bulk-sensitive) HAXPES measurements are in quite good agreement with the nominal concentrations. However, the [Sr]:[Pb] ratios derived from the 2 keV (i.e., more surface-sensitive) measurements are generally higher and increasingly deviate from the nominal for Sr concentrations $\geq 0.5\%$. This trend indicates a Sr rich MAPbI₃ surface with significant Sr surface segregation for 1% and 2% Sr doping.

Figure 2

Figure 2. X-ray-based chemical characterizations. (a) Sr and (b) Mg doping levels as determined from the [Sr]:[Pb] and [Mg]:[Pb] ratio derived from the Sr 3p_{3/2}/Pb 4f_{7/2} and Mg 1s/Pb 4f_{7/2} hard X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (HAXPES) data of the investigated sample series measured with 2 and 6 keV. No values are provided for samples for which the dopant signal could not be separated from the spectral background (due to insufficient signal-to-noise ratio and being below the detection limit). Top view of nano X-ray fluorescence (nXRF) elemental concentration maps of (c) 1% and 2% Sr-doped MAPbI₃ thin film and (d) 0.2% Sr-doped MAPbI₃ thin film. The color scale indicates the amount of Sr present in the investigated area in $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. Their corresponding ratio maps between Sr and Pb of (e) 1% and 2% Sr-doped MAPbI₃ thin film and (f) 0.2% Sr-doped MAPbI₃ thin film in which the ratio is presented by the color scale on the right side of the figure.

For the Mg 1s line, the measurements using 2 and 6 keV have IMFP of ≈ 2 nm and ≈ 8 nm, respectively. The calculated [Mg]:[Pb] ratios computed from the 2 and 6 keV measurements mainly agree with the nominal doping concentrations within the experimental uncertainty as can be seen in [Figure 2b](#). However, unlike Sr doping series, the comparison between the two measurements of different probing depths may indicate (if at all present) a less pronounced Mg surface enrichment. The 5% Mg-doped sample is a notable exception. For this sample, the HAXPES derived composition is the same as determined for the 2% Mg-doped MAPbI₃ and thus below the nominal doping concentration, which can be an indication for grain boundary accumulation requiring further investigation in our next study.

To further test for the nonuniform distribution profile of dopants at different doping concentration in the perovskite layer, we made use of spatially resolved synchrotron-based nano X-ray fluorescence (nXRF) mapping. nXRF is more bulk-sensitive than HAXPES and offers an opportunity to obtain the lateral elemental distribution within the film. [Figure 2c,d](#) shows the surface elemental distribution imaging of the perovskite film at Sr doping levels of 1% together with 2% and 0.2% corresponding to the two different doping regimes that we proposed earlier. The relatively low fluorescence yield of Mg(36) means that its presence at this low concentration cannot be detected by the measurement; hence, only Sr doping series are presented here. With a doping concentration of 1% and even more pronounced in the 2% map ([Figure 2c](#)), evidence of segregation as bright feature of Sr-rich phases is observed, similar to reports by Lau et al.(21) and Caprioglio et al.(22) To compare with HAXPES data, we plot ratio maps of [Sr]:[Pb]. Although the average values of [Sr]:[Pb] agree well with the nominal concentration in [Figure 2e](#), the [Sr]:[Pb] is significantly higher in the localized regions (up to 8% in the 2% Sr-doped sample map). These regions of increased Sr content may explain the Sr enrichment suggested by the HAXPES analysis. We cannot detect clear Sr agglomeration for doping level in the low doping regime. The 0.2% sample in [Figure 2d](#) shows a reasonably uniform distribution of Sr over the investigated area with approximately 0.2% [Sr]:[Pb] ([Figure 2f](#)). The small intensity variation of this particular map is likely due to a slightly inhomogeneous sample, which is corroborated by the Pb map ([Figure S5](#)). Thus, we conclude that Sr can be incorporated in the perovskite lattice, but the ability to host Sr saturates at a concentration lower than 1%.

[Figure 3a](#) and [Figure 3b](#) show the grazing incidence X-ray diffraction (GIXRD) patterns, which confirm the tetragonal phase of MAPbI₃ in all the Sr and Mg-doped samples agreeing with the theoretically calculated pattern ([Figure 3a](#)).(38) Upon the addition of Sr²⁺ and Mg²⁺, no new peaks are detected, which indicates that no new crystalline phases are formed (although signals from the ITO substrate and PbI₂ are present in some cases; see [SI](#) for the related discussion). Thus, GIXRD does not detect any secondary phase segregated at the sample surface (as suggested by nXRF and HAXPES data of the highly Sr-doped MAPbI₃ samples, see [Figure 2](#)), suggesting that the surface phase is amorphous or too thin/too dispersed to be detected by GIXRD. (The GIXRD detection limit for the used setup is estimated to be 0.5% of the probed volume.) Nonetheless, foreign cations may still be incorporated into the perovskite lattice. To detect if any inclusion occurred, we conducted a Le Bail refinement of the GIXRD patterns (fits are reported in [Figure S6a](#) and [Figure S23, SI](#))(39) to characterize the microstrain due to doping. The effect of crystallite size broadening is also included in the refinement (see [Methods section](#) for more details). The contributions on the peak broadening from microstrain and crystallite size are further graphically shown in Williamson–Hall plots ([Figure S6b, SI](#)).

Figure 3

Figure 3. Structural characterization. Grazing incidence X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of (a) Sr doping series (including the theoretical calculation of MAPbI₃) and (b) Mg doping series. (c) Schematic of macrostrain, which causes a peak shift in XRD pattern, and microstrain, which causes peak broadening (illustration adapted from ref (37)). Microstrain values obtained by Le Bail refinement of (d) the Sr doped MAPbI₃ and (e) the Mg-doped MAPbI₃ sample series as a function of nominal dopant concentration. The depicted microstrain values are the mean of at least two different samples (individual values are shown in star points next to the mean values), and the stated error bar represents the standard deviation. Spline fits of the values are shown as a guide for visual clarification.

As schematically shown in Figure 3c, the microstrain represents a local distortion of the lattice, which can be detected as a broadening of the peaks. There are no systematic shifts of the XRD peaks (focused and overlapped patterns are shown in Figure S6c,d) indicating the absence of lattice macrostrain or homogeneous changes in the crystal structure. Due to the low concentration of dopants, which can be included in the perovskite lattice, the small number of doped unit cells compared to the coherent domain can only be shown by the microstrain or inhomogeneous strain. The microstrain evolution of the Sr (Figure 3d) and Mg (Figure 3e) doping series shows that the perovskite phase exhibits increasing lattice distortion up to a specific doping level, above which the lattice relaxes back when the segregation of the second phase starts. In particular, the microstrain of Sr-doped samples reaches a maximum value at 0.2% and quickly drops at higher concentrations, where segregation dominates the doping process (see HAXPES and nXRF data related discussion in conjunction with Figure 2 above). The microstrain at this high doping regime, specifically 2%, declines to a value of 0.07%, similar to the undoped sample's level. As is clearly evident from Figure S6e, the lattice parameters of MAPbI₃ change upon Sr doping in both directions of the tetragonal unit cell implying lattice inclusion. Therefore, we have strong evidence that at 0.2% Sr doping concentration, the dopant can be incorporated into the perovskite lattice. As can be seen in Figure 2, HAXPES and nXRF have different probing volumes, but derived ratios are similar within the uncertainty (1±0.5% and 0.2% respectively). Thus, this [Sr]:[Pb] ratio can give an indication of the amount of Sr in the perovskite crystal, which is less than 1%. However, we acknowledge that a precise amount of Sr requires a further investigation in a follow up study.

In the Mg doping series, the microstrain shows a more gradual decrease after the maximum is reached at 1% doping concentration. This might indicate that lattice incorporation and lattice relaxation due to segregation can happen simultaneously at concentrations higher than 1%. This is in agreement with the HAXPES derived conclusion of a less pronounced Mg surface segregation. Hence, Mg doping can have a higher threshold until the surface segregation occurs. Noticeably, the most significant microstrain occurs at a higher doping concentration in the case of Mg (1%) than in the case of Sr (0.2%), with higher absolute values in the Mg case. Besides, as can be seen in [Figure S6f](#), the lattice indicates a contraction in the c-direction with the most significant change at 1% Mg, which is different from uniform changes in the Sr-doped perovskite lattice in both directions, shown in [Figure S6e](#). The difference can originate from the smaller ionic radius of Mg^{2+} (72 pm) compared to that of Sr^{2+} (118 pm) and Pb^{2+} (119 pm),⁽¹⁶⁾ which influences the ability to incorporate the doping atom into the perovskite lattice. Notably, our DFT calculations predict very similar Pb–I and Sr–I average bond lengths of 320 and 323 pm in pristine and Sr-doped (substitutional Sr_{Pb}) perovskites, while shorter Mg–I bond of 298 pm is reported in Mg-doped (substitutional Mg_{Pb}) systems, in agreement with the tabulated ionic radii from Shannon et al.⁽¹⁶⁾ The comparison of the microstrain trend in the case of Sr doping with the corresponding HAXPES data in [Figure 2](#) corroborates our hypothesis above that the dopant is incorporated into the perovskite lattice until a critical distortion is reached. Then, the dopant starts to segregate at the surface, resulting in a relaxation of the perovskite lattice.

We investigated how different doping regime influences the position of the valence band maximum (VBM) concerning the E_{F} using HAXPES. [Figure 4a](#) and [Figure 4b](#) show the VBM position of the investigated Sr-doped and Mg-doped MAPbI_3 sample series, respectively (full spectra and details on VBM determination are shown in [Figure S4, SI](#)). Assuming that the bandgap (E_{g}) at the surface of the sample is the same as its optical E_{g} (i.e., ≈ 1.6 eV obtained from Tauc plots of corresponding UV–vis spectra shown in [Figure S7, SI](#)), the undoped MAPbI_3 would exhibit a (slight) n-type character on the sample surface. By adding dopants, similar trends can be detected in the VBM position as a function of dopant concentration for 2 and 6 keV measurements. At low doping levels (i.e., lower than 0.5% Sr- and 2% Mg-doped, indicated by the blue area in [Figure 4a](#) and [Figure 4b](#)), the films become more n-type compared to the undoped MAPbI_3 , whereas with higher doping concentration, the VBM shifts closer to E_{F} , which would be in agreement with a less n-type character. Note that in this doping concentration regime segregated surface phases and—independent of doping concentration—the presence of metallic lead (Pb^0) could also impact the position of the VBM compared to E_{F} . However, we do not expect either to have a significant impact (see [SI](#) for detailed discussion).

Figure 4

Figure 4. Influence of dopants on electronic properties. Position of the valence band maximum (VBM) of the studied MAPbI_3 samples concerning the Fermi level (E_{F}) for various nominal doping concentrations of (a) Sr and (b) Mg derived from 2 and 6 keV HAXPES data. The region in which the doped perovskite is more n-type compared to the

undoped material is indicated in blue, whereas less n-type region is shown in yellow. The dashed line denotes the value obtained for the undoped samples. The fraction of metallic lead (Pb^0) compared to the total amount of lead at the surface of the samples, as determined by 2 keV HAXPES measurements, is shown in (c) for the Sr and in (d) for the Mg-doped MAPbI₃ sample series. The experimental uncertainty is presented as the area along with the corresponding spline fits of the values as a guide for visual clarification.

Notably, even the small changes in absolute Sr concentration from 0.1% Sr to 0.5% Sr-doped causes a VBM shift from 1.04 ± 0.1 eV to 0.97 ± 0.1 eV concerning E_F , tending toward the VBM of the undoped sample. This tendency is similar for 1% and 2% Mg-doped samples. It indicates that different concentration regimes of *one* dopant can vary the n-type doping level. We can correlate the reasons behind this change to the change in defect concentrations of the films as the number of dominant vacancies can induce n or p-doping of perovskite.⁽³¹⁾ Together with theoretical calculation (discussed in detail in [SI](#)), we postulate that the dopants included in the lattice can passivate Pb ($V_{\text{Pb}^{2-}}$) and MA (V_{MA^-}) vacancies. This can result in a more n-type material, whereas less n-type doping might be realized by the increase in iodine interstitials (I_i^-) due to the iodine excess in the precursors in this case. The DFT calculation shows that the $V_{\text{Pb}^{2-}}$ passivation is favored by 0.24 and 0.11 eV for Sr^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , respectively. This scenario would be in agreement with the significant reduction of the Pb^0 content in the sample upon doping shown in [Figure 4c](#) and [Figure 4d](#). After Pb^{2+} site is saturated with Sr^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , the n-type doping can further be a result of V_{MA^-} passivation with the formation energy of -0.44 and 0.01 eV, respectively. Furthermore, since Mg^{2+} has a higher inclusion concentration than Sr^{2+} despite its unfavorable tolerance factor to form 3D MA-based perovskite, it indicates a plausible scenario of Mg^{2+} included stably in interstitial position.

Device Performance

To study the impact of the dopants on the performance of complete solar cells, we prepared p-i-n devices made of ITO/PTAA/MAPbI₃/C₆₀/BCP/Cu, as previously reported (see [Methods section](#)).⁽⁴¹⁾ [Figure 5a,b](#) display the device's open circuit voltage (V_{OC}) as a function of the doping level for Sr and Mg (full set of parameters are presented in [Figure S13, SI](#)). Remarkably, the microstrain of the perovskite lattice reported in [Figure 3](#), which we replotted here, follows the V_{OC} trend. In particular, we observe a maximum in both microstrain and V_{OC} at 0.2% Sr- and 1% Mg-doped devices, and a (slight) decrease after the maximum has been reached. It is worth noticing that at high Sr doping levels (more than 0.5% Sr), the microstrain decreases to the undoped level, yet V_{OC} is still improved compared to undoped devices. This can be attributed to possible surface passivation by the Sr surface phase segregation also seen in the literature.^(20,22)

Figure 5

*Data from Chen et al.

Figure 5. Device performance upon doping. Correlation between open circuit voltage (V_{OC}) of solar cell devices with microstrain from GIXRD refinement of (a) the Sr-doped MAPbI₃ series and (b) the Mg-doped MAPbI₃ series. (c) Open circuit voltage trend with respect to nominal doping concentration of 3 alkaline earth metal ions, namely, Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, and Sr²⁺ (data for Ca²⁺ doping is collected from Chen et al.)⁽⁴⁰⁾ (d) Current density–voltage (J – V) curve of the best 0.2% Sr-doped with antireflection coating and undoped MAPbI₃ device measured at standard AM1.5 1 sun equivalent condition with a 100 mV/s scan rate. Arrows indicate scan direction. The inset is continuous maximum power point tracking in N₂ at 25 °C, in simulated global AM1.5 solar spectrum with UV cut-off at 380 nm for 24 h.

This similar trend between V_{OC} and microstrain indicates the positive impact of lattice incorporation of the dopants to reduce defect concentration in MAPbI₃. As mentioned in the previous section, the DFT calculations predict defect passivation by incorporating Sr²⁺ and Mg²⁺ (see [SI](#) for details), which can explain the high V_{OC} with lattice incorporation of the dopants. We further calculated quasi-Fermi level splitting of perovskite layer and reinforced that the voltage improvement stems from bulk defect passivation rather than interfacial passivation at low doping concentration (see [Figure S14](#) and related discussion in [SI](#)). Furthermore, we extend the analysis of the V_{OC} trend to literature data to include Ca into the series of dopants. The data points of Ca₂ doping are plotted from Chen et al. with similar doping concentration range.⁽⁴⁰⁾ [Figure 5c](#) shows the relative change in V_{OC} of Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, and Sr²⁺ doped devices as a function of doping concentration. Although the trend of V_{OC} is similar for all three dopants, the highest V_{OC} occurs at 1% for Mg, 0.5% for Ca,⁽⁴⁰⁾ and 0.2% for Sr doping. Interestingly, this trend corresponds to the pattern of effective radii of the dopants as well (Mg²⁺ (72 pm) < Ca²⁺ (100 pm) < Sr²⁺ (118 pm)).⁽¹⁶⁾ Thus, the highest V_{OC} happens at a higher doping concentration for dopants with smaller ionic radii, which implies that the ability to host dopants in MAPbI₃ depends on the radii of the dopants.

The low doping regime where the dopants can be included in the perovskite lattice and passivate defects results in better device performance. In particular, upon Sr and Mg doping, the average V_{OC} improves by about 100 mV (from 1023 mV on average for undoped devices to more than 1117 mV and 1125 mV on average for Sr-doped and Mg-doped devices, respectively). Full PV parameters are shown in [Figure S13](#). [Figure 5d](#) displays the champion p-i-n MAPbI₃ device with 0.2% Sr doping, which shows short circuit current density (J_{SC}) of 22.5 mA/cm² (in agreement with integrated current density from external quantum efficiency plot in [Figure S17b](#)), fill factor (FF) of 74.3% and a V_{OC} of 1161 mV, resulting in an efficiency of 19.4% (stabilized at 19%) compared to 17.2% of the best undoped MAPbI₃ device. To further prove the effectiveness of low doping regime, n-i-p 0.2% Sr-doped MAPbI₃ devices were fabricated, resulting in a more than 20% champion device compared to 18.7% of undoped MAPbI₃ device shown in [Figure S19](#). The long-term stability of the doped MAPbI₃ compared to undoped MAPbI₃ is shown in the inset [Figure 5d](#). The transient of the first few hours is suppressed by doping. The Sr-doped device shows a quick transient reaching its maximum power output in 2 h, whereas it takes more than 20 h for the undoped device to reach the stabilized PCE. This trend might be attributed to faster ion migration⁽⁴²⁾ or a reduction of the number of mobile ionic defects upon doping.

Conclusion

In this study, we investigated the doping mechanism of halide perovskites using Sr²⁺ and Mg²⁺ to compare doping elements with similar chemical properties but different ionic radii. We found two distinct doping regimes. The low doping concentration regime, which results in incorporation of the dopant into the perovskite lattice, and the high doping concentration regime, which results in surface phase segregation. We observed that the threshold between the low and the high doping regimes depends on the size of the doping element. In particular, methylammonium lead iodide perovskite can incorporate a larger quantity of Mg²⁺ than Sr²⁺ due to their difference in ionic radius. We discussed the impact of the dopant incorporation and the surface segregation on the n-type character of the materials as the result of the interaction of the doping element with the defect chemistry of the material. Thus, we prove the effectiveness of the low doping regime for the first time, demonstrating MAPbI₃ based solar cells with an open circuit voltage exceeding 1.16 V and stabilized PCE of more than 19% for p-i-n structure and more than 20% PCE for n-i-p solar cells. Our work provides a comprehensive picture of the doping mechanism of halide perovskites semiconductor, which is somewhat different from doping of classical semiconductors.

Methods

Solar Cells Fabrication

All chemicals are used as received. The perovskite solution is mixed from 1.2 M of PbI₂ (Tokyo Chemical Industry), and CH₃NH₃I (Dyename) in mixed solvent DMF:DMSO 6:1 (v:v). The dopant SrI₂ (Alfa Aesar) is dissolved in DMSO (1 M) and MgI₂ (Santa Cruz) is dissolved in DMF:DMSO 6:1 (0.7 M). The amount of dopants in the perovskite solution is calculated according to the molar ratio with PbI₂. The final perovskite solution is shaken at 60 °C for 5 min to dissolve all components.

In-doped SnO₂ (ITO) substrates (Automatic Research, 15 Ω·cm⁻²) are sonicated for 15 min with Mucosol (2% in deionized water), acetone and isopropyl for cleaning and eventually UV-ozone treatment for 15 min. Prior to perovskite deposition, PTAA (poly[bis(4-phenyl)(2,4,6-trimethylphenyl)amine]) (Sigma-Aldrich) with a concentration of 2 mg/mL in toluene is spin-coated on clean substrates (4000 rpm for 30 s). The substrate is then annealed at 100 °C for 10 min. 100 μL of perovskite solution is dropped on room temperature substrate before starting the spin coating program (4000 rpm for 30 s, ramping for 5 s). After 20 s of spin coating, 500 μL of ethyl acetate is dropped on the substrate to form a smooth and compact film. The perovskite film is immediately annealed at 100 °C for 60 min. Finally, C₆₀ (20 nm) (Sigma-Aldrich), BCP (bathocuproine or 2,9-Dimethyl-4,7-diphenyl-1) (10 nm) (Sigma-Aldrich), and Cu (100 nm) (Alfa Aesar, 99.95% purity) are evaporated on the perovskite layer to complete the device. All of these fabrication steps are done in an inert atmosphere with minimized air exposure.

For n-i-p MAPbI₃, the compact TiO₂ is deposited on cleaned F-doped SnO₂ (FTO, 15 Ω·cm⁻²) using a method reported elsewhere.⁽⁴³⁾ In short, the cleaned FTO substrates are submerged in 200 mL TiCl₄ solution at 70 °C for 1 h, then the substrates are cleaned thoroughly with deionized water and dried at 100 °C for 1 h. The TiO₂ layer is treated with UV-ozone for 30 min before perovskite deposition. The hole selective layer is prepared as followed. 36.15 mg of Spiro-OMETAD is dissolved in 1 mL of chlorobenzene, then 14.40 μL 4-*tert*-Butylpyridine (Sigma-Aldrich, 98%), 8.75 μL of Li-TFSI (bis(trifluoromethane)sulfonimide lithium salt, 99.95% trace metals basis, Sigma-Aldrich) (300 mg per mL of acetonitrile), and 14.50 μL FK209 (Co(II) salt, Sigma-Aldrich) (500 mg per mL of acetonitrile) are added to the Spiro-OMETAD solution. Finally, 80 nm of Au (Alfa Aesar, 99.99% purity) is evaporated on top to finish the device.

Hard X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy

Hard X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (HAXPES) measurements were carried out at the HiKE endstation located at the BESSY II KMC-1 beamline at Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB).^(44,45) The HiKE endstation is equipped with a Scienta R4000 electron analyzer and an excitation energy of 2003 eV (referred to as “2 keV”) and 6009 eV (referred to as “6 keV”) were employed. The binding energy (BE) scale of the HAXPES measurements was calibrated by measuring the Au 4f energy region of a clean Au foil in electrical contact with the (grounded) sample and setting the BE of the Au 4f_{7/2} line to 84.0 eV. The pressure in the endstation’s analysis chamber during the HAXPES measurements remained <1 × 10⁻⁸ mbar. Curve fit analysis of measured detail HAXPES spectra were simultaneously conducted using the Fityk software.⁽⁴⁶⁾ Voigt profile functions, along with linear backgrounds, were employed for these fits. Spin-orbit doublets were fitted using two Voigt functions with intensity ratios set to obey the 2j + 1 multiplicity rule. The peak intensities of the HAXPES core levels were corrected to account for differences in photoionization cross section (σ),^(47–49) and when required also for changes in the inelastic mean free path (IMFP),^(34,35) and the transmission function of the electron analyzer (T).⁽⁵⁰⁾ To quantify the Pb 4f spectra, two doublet peak pairs were used to account for the core level contributions and five additional (broader) pairs to account for the satellites’ contribution background (derived from electron energy losses related to valence and conduction band transitions in PbX₂ systems).^(51,52) The Sr 3p signal can be detected in all the Sr doped samples, whereas the Sr 3d signal is only absent for the lowest (0.1%) Sr-doped sample. This apparent difference can be explained by two factors: First, at 2 keV excitation, the σ for the Sr 3p core levels are approximately three times higher than that of Sr 3d core levels in our experimental setup.⁽⁴⁷⁾ Moreover, in contrast to the Sr 3p core levels, which have a linear background, the Sr 3d core levels directly overlap with the Pb 4f_{7/2} line, the most prominent Pb-related photoelectron line at the used excitation energy, which explains why the Sr 3d signal is below the detection limit at low Sr concentrations (i.e., 0.1% doping). For these reasons, although the close energetic proximity of the Pb 4f/Sr 3d core levels would present a straightforward opportunity to quantify the [Sr]:[Pb] ratios just by normalizing the signal of each core level by its corresponding σ,⁽⁴⁷⁾ we chose to calculate the [Sr]:[Pb] ratios from the more prominent core lines (i.e., Sr 3p_{3/2} and Pb 4f_{7/2}). The HAXPES probing depth is governed by the IMFP of the probed photoelectrons. The main contribution stems from the surface of the sample, which decays exponentially to 1/e within IMFP. For the Sr 3p and Pb 4f lines, the measurements using 2 and 6 keV have an IMFP of ≈4 nm and ≈10 nm, respectively.^(48,49) For the Mg 1s line, the measurements using 2 and 6 keV have IMFP values of ≈2 nm and ≈8 nm, respectively.^(48,49) The position of the valence band maximum (VBM) with respect to the Fermi level (E_F) was determined by linear approximation of the leading edge of the valence band spectra shown in [Figure S4](#).

Nano X-ray Fluorescence

The synchrotron-based nano X-ray fluorescence (nXRF) measurements for the elemental mapping of the perovskite films were done in the 2-ID-D beamline at an excitation energy of 16 keV, X-ray step size of 0.15 μm, and a dwell time of 50 ms at the Advanced Photon Source, Argonne National Laboratory. The MAPS software, written in IDL programming language, was used to display the acquired XRF data. Because Sr is commonly found in glass substrates (e.g., the used ITO-coated glass substrate), the perovskite films employed in the nXRF analysis were prepared on quartz substrates, following the same procedure detailed in the [Solar Cells Fabrication](#) subsection above. The purpose of the

measurement is to check the possibility of two doping regimes. We chose 0.2%, 1%, and 2% to have at least 1 order of magnitude difference in doping concentration for the two regimes.

Density Functional Theory Calculations

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations have been carried out by modeling defects in the $2 \times 2 \times 2$ supercell of MAPbI₃, by fixing cell parameters to the experimental values.⁽⁵³⁾ Energies of formation and reaction of Sr and Mg related defects have been calculated by using the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE)⁽⁵⁴⁾ exchange-correlation functional and ultrasoft pseudopotentials with a cutoff on the wave functions of 40 Ryd (320 Ryd on the charge density) sampling the Brillouin zone (BZ) at the Gamma point. Defects formation energies diagrams of Sr and Mg defects in MAPbI₃ (Figure S9) have been calculated at the PBE level by following a widely used approach and by simulating I-medium conditions of growth of the perovskite.^(55,56) The chemical potentials of Sr and Mg have been calculated by imposing the equilibrium with the relative precursors, i.e., $\mu(\text{Mg}/\text{Sr}) = \mu(\text{MgI}_2/\text{SrI}_2) - 2\mu(\text{I})$, where $\mu(\text{I})$ is calculated in I-medium conditions and is set according to thermodynamic equilibrium between MAPbI₃ and PbI₂.

Thermodynamic ionization levels in Figure S8 and the plots of Kohn–Sham orbitals have been calculated by performing single point calculations at the HSE06-SOC⁽⁵⁷⁾ level of theory (exchange fraction $\alpha = 0.43$, dispersion included a posteriori through the DFT-D3 scheme⁽⁵⁸⁾) on the equilibrium geometries found at the PBE level.⁽⁵⁶⁾ Hybrid calculations have been performed by using norm conserving pseudopotentials with an energy cutoff of 40 Ryd on the wave functions and by sampling the BZ at the Gamma point.⁽⁵⁶⁾

Grazing Incident X-ray Diffraction

The measurement is conducted in air with the PANalytical X'Pert Pro MPD (multipurpose diffractometer) using grazing incidence geometry. Grazing incident X-ray diffraction (GIXRD) patterns are collected with a step size of 0.02 degree, for 10 s each step. On the basis of the signal-to-noise ratio of the collected GIXRD data, we estimate a detection limit of 0.5% crystalline phase in the probed volume.

The Le Bail method was chosen instead of the Rietveld refinement method due to the ease in the calculation without a requirement of the exact atomic positions and the scattering power of the atoms, hence reducing the computation effort.⁽³⁹⁾ The refinement is done with the FULLPROF program. Here, we could use the full line profile analysis because our XRD patterns show all theoretically predicted peaks from the lattice structure of the material. Different from the standard material, in the polycrystalline film, the XRD peaks can be described by pseudo-Voigt functions. The function is used to consider both Gaussian and Lorentzian contribution to the shape of the peaks in the pattern. Hence, we assume that the angular dependence microstrain will affect to Gaussian peak broadening contribution (the case of Lorentzian contribution to microstrain is rare, so it was excluded from the analysis), whereas the broadening due to crystallite size is from Lorentzian contribution.⁽⁵⁹⁾ From this Gaussian contribution, the microstrain is calculated. More details on the refinement can be found in the SI.

Photoluminescence Characterization

Absolute photoluminescence (PL) spectra were recorded from hyperspectral images with a custom setup described elsewhere.⁽⁶⁰⁾ We used two 450 nm LEDs for excitation whose fluence are calibrated to 1 sun equivalent and a calibrated CCD camera was used to collect PL emission, coupled to a tunable liquid crystal filter. The setup was calibrated to absolute photon numbers with light sources of known fluences,⁽⁶¹⁾ thus enabling to estimate the quasi Fermi-level splitting (QFLS) from the generalized Planck law using the high-energy tail fit method of the PL spectra.⁽⁶²⁾

Current Density–Voltage Measurement

The J – V measurement is done with 1 sun equivalent illumination from an Oriel LCS-100 class ABB solar simulator in an inert atmosphere without cooling. The device's active area is 0.16 cm². The lamp is calibrated with a Silicon 1 cm² diode certified by Fraunhofer ISE.

External Quantum Efficiency (EQE) Measurement

The EQE is measured with a Newport 300 W xenon arc lamp using TracQ software in an Oriel Instruments QEPVSI-b system. A Newport Cornerstone 260 monochromator is used to create monochromatic light chopped at a frequency of 78 Hz. Before the measurement, the system is calibrated with a silicon reference cell with a known spectral response. The electrical response of the device is recorded with a Stanford Research SR830 Lock-In amplifier and evaluated using TracQ.

Ultraviolet–Visible Spectrophotometry

Transmittance and reflectance of the samples are measured with a PerkinElmer Lambda 1050 spectrophotometer equipped with a tungsten-halogen lamp. The measurement is done with a wavelength range of 300 to 850 nm. The derived optical bandgap from the Tauc plot of a direct bandgap material (relation between $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ and $h\nu$) is the intercept between the linear approximation of the absorption edge with the background.

Scanning Electron Microscopy

The images are collected with Hitachi S-4100 at 5 kV acceleration voltage and 30k magnification to obtain top view and cross sectional images.

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/jacs.9b11637>.

- Full HAXPES spectra of investigated energies; Top view of nXRF; More information on XRD; Details of DFT calculation; Photovoltaic parameters of solar cells; SEM images; PL measurement ([PDF](#))

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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